

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Empowering the construction of the honor system for university faculties with the spirit of educationist

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Abstract

The honor of teaching staff is not only the affirmation and recognition of the achievements of teaching and administrative staff, but also the important incentive for building a high-quality professional group of teaching and administrative staff with noble ethics, excellent teaching skills, rational structure and full of vitality. At present, there are some difficulties in the construction of university faculty honor system, such as the absence of top-level design, outdated underlying logic, and insufficient role playing. By cultivating noble teachers' morality and ethos and the spirit of educationist, and empowering the construction of the honor system of university faculty with the spirit of educationist, we can promote the construction of university faculty, and provide strong support for the modernization of education, the construction of a powerful country of higher education, and developing education that people are satisfied with.

Keywords: The Spirit of Educationist; Honor System; University; Teaching and Administrative Staff; Higher Education

1. Introduction

With the continuous deepening of higher education reform, how to stimulate the endogenous motivation of university faculties has become an important issue. The honor system, as an important incentive mechanism, plays an irreplaceable role in affirming the value of teachers, setting an example and benchmark, and consolidating the strength of the group of teaching and administrative staff. Integrating the spirit of educationist into the construction of the honor system not only injects deep value guidance into the honor system, but also guides university faculties to cultivate noble professional ethics continuously, improve their educational abilities, enhance their sense of social responsibility in the pursuit of honor, and ultimately achieve resonance between personal growth and the development of higher education.

2. The necessity of the construction of the honor system for university faculties

2.1. The inevitable demand of epoch development

In the international competition dominated by knowledge economy and technological innovation, colleges and universities, as the key source of knowledge innovation, the core position of talent cultivation and the important support of social services, have a decisive impact on the effectiveness of the 'double first-class' construction by their professional quality and internal drive of teacher's group. The traditional management mode guided by institutional constraints and the task of indicators has significant limitations in activating teachers' innovative potential and cultivating educators' spirit. Constructing the honor system of university faculties is an inevitable requirement with the development of the age. Through the systematic honor incentive mechanism, it meets the demand for respect for talent value in the era of

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knowledge economy, accurately anchors teachers' professional achievements and social contributions, closely connects personal professional values with national strategic needs, and also stimulates teachers to participate in education and teaching reform with a higher sense of mission, finally forms a benign ecology of promoting development with honor and gathering advantages with spirit.

2.2. The internal need to facilitate students' growth

As the key guide for students' growth, teachers of universities undertake the multiple missions of imparting professional knowledge, cultivating students' proper values, and fostering students' innovative thinking and practical capabilities. Under the honor system, the selected excellent teachers show significant benchmark value in the dimensions of teaching innovation, education concept and student care. Through honor recognition and typical publicity, these excellent educational practices can become a living sample of peer learning, and promote the common improvement of teaching quality and education level. For students, the in-depth interaction with teachers of great honor means not only obtaining higher quality educational resources, but also immersing them in a strong academic atmosphere and noble teachers' ethics, imperceptibly stimulating their internal drive for learning and innovative potential, helping to cultivate compound talents with a sense of social responsibility, innovative spirit and practical ability, and injecting a steady stream of high-quality talents into social development.

2.3. Effective ways to promote teachers' professional development

The honor system is the core incentive mechanism to drive the professional development of university faculties, and its value is reflected in the dual dimensions of goal orientation and achievement feedback. From the perspective of goal oriented, the honor selection criteria form a dynamic guide: teachers are required to actively innovate the educational concept in the teaching field, and construct an immersive classroom ecology through innovative methods such as blending teaching and project-based learning; In the scientific research dimension, teachers are encouraged to anchor the frontier of disciplines, carry out original research from an interdisciplinary perspective, and generate breakthrough academic achievements. From the perspective of achievement feedback, the spiritual rewards and material support given by the honor system not only significantly enhance teachers' sense of professional dignity, but also build a virtuous circle of teachers' professional development- after teachers obtain value recognition, they will further strengthen their internal drive for professional development, accelerate the transformation from experienced teachers to expert educators, and ultimately promote the overall quality of university teachers to achieve a qualitative leap.

2.4. Important measures to promote the overall development of universities

From the strategic perspective of university organization development, teacher honor system has become the strategic fulcrum to enhance the core competitiveness and shape the brand image. First, the value identity ecology constructed by the honor system can form a strong talent attraction effect. In the current market-oriented allocation of talent resources, the system design with honor incentive as the core is gradually becoming an important indicator for high-level talents' career choice. Excellent educators are more inclined to choose a university platform with perfect honor incentive mechanism which can realize their professional value and obtain spiritual satisfaction, so as to inject innovative vitality into the teaching staff. Second, the honor system can stimulate the endogenous motivation of teachers by creating a benign competitive environment of 'emulating each other'. When honor evaluation is deeply bound with professional development, teachers will spontaneously form an academic community in which teaching and learning grow together in the process of pursuing honor, and promote the formation of a dense atmosphere of academic innovation. This positive incentive can not only improve the quality of curriculum construction and promote scientific research achievements, but also continuously enhance the comprehensive strength of universities in the fields of talent training, scientific research, social services and cultural inheritance, and help universities improve their international influence.

2.5. Macro demand for serving national strategic development

In the era context of the in-depth promotion of the national strategy, colleges and universities, as the cradle of talent cultivation and the source of scientific and technological innovation, shoulder the historical mission of providing intellectual support and talent safeguarding for the realization of Chinese modernization. The honor system of university faculties can effectively guide teachers to deeply combine their personal academic pursuit with the major strategic needs of the country by building a value-oriented incentive mechanism. The honor system encourages teachers to actively carry out cutting-edge research and innovative teaching practice by commending advanced models and setting up value benchmarks, so as to foster a motivational climate scientific research and a talent training orientation of 'educating talents for the country'. This mechanism not only helps to cultivate innovative talents who adapt to industrial change and social development, and produce scientific research achievements with independent intellectual property rights, but also drives industrial upgrading with knowledge innovation, serves national development with

talent advantages, helps to achieve high-level scientific and technological self-reliance and high-quality social development, and highlights the era responsibility of higher education serving the national strategy.

3. The connotation of the spirit of educationist

Educationist spirit is a precious spiritual wealth condensed by educators in the long-term educational practice, which has rich and profound connotation. It covers:

The ideal and belief of having a big heart and serving the country sincerely: educators are required to closely connect their personal career with the fate of the country, and to serve the country and the people as the highest pursuit of education; The moral sentiment of 'speaking as a scholar and acting as a model of the world': it emphasizes that educators should become the moral model of students in their words and deeds, and infect and influence others with noble morality; The educational wisdom of enlightening the mind and nourishing the soul in accordance with their aptitude: education should not only impart knowledge, but also enlighten students' wisdom, nourish students' soul, and carry out targeted education according to students' personality differences; The attitude of diligent study and earnest practice, seeking truth and pursuing innovation: educators are encouraged to maintain the desire for knowledge and persistence in practice, and constantly pursue truth and innovation in education and teaching; The benevolent heart of enjoying teaching, loving students and being willing to dedicate: education is a cause full of love, educators should love education, care about students' growth, and selflessly contribute their strength to the cause of education; The pursuit of propagating the Dao, with a heart for the world and educating people through culture: we should not only pay attention to the individual development of students, but also focus on social progress and the inheritance of human civilization.

4. The correspondence between the spirit of educationist and the goal of honor system construction

4.1. Encourage teachers to practice ideals and beliefs

One of the core objectives of the honor system for university faculties is to activate the endogenous motivation of teachers' participation in education. The ideal and belief of 'bearing the greater good in mind and serving the country with absolute sincerity' in the spirit of educationist has injected a distinct value orientation into the honor system. When the honor selection includes indicators such as serving the country's major strategic needs and cultivating talents in short supply, it is not only a high recognition of teachers' individual achievements, but also a deep integration of personal career ideals and national education cause. The recognition of teachers who have made outstanding contributions to the bottlenecks of technology research can encourage more educators to strengthen their ideals and beliefs and contribute to the construction of an educational power in their respective posts.

4.2. Guide teachers to improve their moral cultivation

As an important value oriented mechanism, the honor system must strengthen the consideration of teachers' moral quality. The spirit of educationist advocates 'words as a model for scholars, deeds as an example for the world', which is highly consistent with the internal requirements of the construction of teachers' professional ethics. In the honor system, teachers who strictly abide by academic norms, care for students' growth, and practice the code of ethics can be commended, which can set a moral benchmark in the group of teachers. This demonstration effect will encourage more teachers to consciously cultivate noble teachers' morality, infiltrate students' hearts with personality charm, and finally create a clean and positive educational environment.

4.3. Improve teachers' mode of nurturing talents

The educational wisdom with the core of 'enlightening wisdom and moistening the mind and teaching students in accordance with their aptitude' is not only an important embodiment of the spirit of educationist, but also a key dimension of the construction of the honor system. By setting up characteristic awards such as 'Teaching Innovation Award', teachers are encouraged to break through the traditional teaching mode and pay attention to students' personality differences. Giving honor incentives to teachers who stimulate students' innovative thinking and significantly improve students' practical ability through precise guidance can promote student-centered teaching reform boom and cultivate more high-quality talents with innovative spirit.

4.4. Encourage teachers to pursue innovative

In the face of the rapid changes of the times, teachers need to uphold the attitude of studying diligently, practicing earnestly, seeking truth and pursuing innovation. The honor system can give more commendations to teachers who

have made breakthroughs in the frontier fields of disciplines and promoted the innovation of teaching models by setting up special honors for scientific innovation. This incentive mechanism will stimulate teachers' enthusiasm to continuously learn new knowledge and explore new methods, promote the continuous rise of scientific research level in universities, and provide intellectual support for scientific innovation and social development.

4.5. Strengthen teachers' dedication

The benevolent heart of taking pleasure in teaching, loving students and being willing to contribute and the grand pursuit of bearing the world in mind and educating people through culture highlight the humanistic feelings and social responsibilities of educators. The honor system should focus on rewarding the 'light-bearer' who have long been rooted in the front line of teaching and devoted themselves to education, as well as teachers who have made outstanding contributions to cultural communication and international educational exchanges. Through honor incentive, teachers' sense of professional mission will be further strengthened, and they will be guided to continue to cultivate new people with international vision and national feelings.

5. Ensure the fairness of the construction of honor system

5.1. Scientific setting of evaluation indicators

When constructing the honor system of university teachers, the setting of evaluation indicators is very important. A single quantitative index should be avoided, such as the number of scientific research papers and project funds. When establishing the honor system, we should comprehensively consider the teaching quality, the innovation and practical application value of scientific research achievements, social service contribution, teachers' ethics and other dimensions. For example, teaching quality evaluation can be combined with students' evaluation of teaching, peer evaluation, teaching supervision evaluation and teachers' actual performance in teaching method innovation; The evaluation of scientific research achievements should not only focus on the number of published papers, but also pay attention to the citation rate of papers, the innovation of scientific research projects and the role of promoting the development of disciplines; Social service contributions include teachers' participation in local economic construction, providing technical support to enterprises, and carrying out public welfare education activities. Through the scientific and reasonable setting of evaluation indicators, the honor system can reflect the work performance and comprehensive quality of teachers to ensure the fairness.

5.2. Improve the review mechanism

Establishing and improving a fair and transparent evaluation mechanism is the key to ensure the fairness of the honor system. The review process shall strictly follow the established procedures and standards to avoid the interference of human factors. The selection of evaluation experts should be widely representative, covering senior scholars in different disciplines, famous teachers and education management experts. At the same time, clarify the responsibilities and powers of the review experts, establish the corresponding supervision mechanism, and supervise the whole review process to ensure the fairness and transparency of the review process. For example, a special review and supervision committee is established to accept teachers' complaints about the review results, investigate and handle violations in the review process, and ensure the credibility of the review results.

5.3. Dynamic adjustment evaluation criteria

With the renewal of educational philosophy, the change of social needs and the development of colleges and universities, the evaluation criteria of University Teachers' honor system should keep pace with the times and be dynamically adjusted. Regularly evaluate and optimize the evaluation indicators and weights to better adapt to the new educational situation and development requirements. With the wide application of information technology in the field of education, teachers' ability to use modern educational technology to carry out teaching activities should also be included in the scope of evaluation, and its proportion in the evaluation system should be adjusted according to the actual development situation, so as to ensure that the honor system can continuously encourage teachers to improve their own ability.

6. Conclusion

It is of great practical significance to endow the construction of honor system for university faculties with the spirit of educationist. By clarifying the necessity of constructing the honor system for university teachers, deeply excavating the role of educationist spirit, and paying attention to fairness, we can build a scientific, reasonable and effective honor system for university teachers. This can not only stimulate the enthusiasm and creativity of teachers, promote the high-quality development of higher education, but also provide a solid guarantee for the cultivation of socialist builders and

successors with all-round development of morality, intelligence, physique, art and labor. In the future practice, universities should continue to explore and improve the teacher honor system, give full play to the leading role of the spirit of educationist, and inject new vitality into the development of higher education.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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